

Chemical Reactivity and Light Absorption. Part II.

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From considerations based on several chemical reactions, it was concluded in Part I of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 23) that an increase in chemical reactivity of a molecule is associated with increased light absorption. The weakening of the binding forces of molecules, due to the presence of molecules of another substance, leads to an increase in the light absorption.

We have carried on further work on this subject and the results and conclusions are recorded in this paper. We have measured the light absorption of different reacting substances separately and in mixtures by photographing their absorption spectra with Hilger quartz spectrographs using a copper arc as the light source. The exposure for taking the photograph varied from 7—30 seconds. The amount of chemical change during the period of exposure was negligible and hence the products formed as the result of the chemical change from the reacting mixtures did not play any important part in affecting the light absorption. Moreover, in many cases, the light absorption by the resultants is less than those of the reacting substances.

Reactions involving Chlorine.

(a) *Chlorine and hydrogen.*—Some years ago Weigert and Kellermann (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1923, 107, 1) obtained some interesting results on the light absorption by a mixture of chlorine and hydrogen. They took a cinematograph exposure of a small cell filled with chlorine and hydrogen and illuminated by a spark discharge giving out intense light. As long as there was no chemical reaction between chlorine and hydrogen on illumination, a photograph of the cell, which appeared to be empty, was obtained on the film but when the reaction started and in the course of about 1/50 second, a cloud developed in the reaction mixture and the increased light absorption due to the occurrence of the cloud or the fog in the mixture of hydrogen and chlorine was recorded on the cinematograph film. This observation

of Weigert and Kellermann, which has been adduced by Bodenstein (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1925, 21, 532) and others as evidence of chain reactions, appears to us to be a case of the weakening of the binding forces of the chlorine molecules due to the presence of hydrogen and the consequent increase in light absorption by the system and supports our view that an increase in the chemical reactivity is associated with increased light absorption.

(b) *Oxalic acid and chlorine*.—This photochemical reaction has been investigated by Bhattacharya and Dhar (*J. Chim. phys.*, 1929, 26, 556). In absence of hydrochloric acid, the reaction is extremely rapid and hence the reaction has been studied in presence of hydrochloric acid, which was added to the chlorine water. Fig. 1 shows that the light absorption by a mixture of chlorine water and oxalic acid solution is greater than the absorptions by chlorine water and oxalic acid considered separately.

Moreover, we have shown that this reaction is appreciably accelerated by radiations of wave-lengths 5650, 7304 and 8500Å, although the limits of sensitised decomposition and photochemical dissociation for chlorine molecules are 5000 and 4780Å respectively. Hence in presence of oxalic acid, the decomposition of chlorine molecules is markedly sensitised and these molecules become reactive in radiations of wave-lengths longer than the sensitised and the photochemical dissociation limits. Along with this increased reactivity of chlorine molecules, a marked increase of light absorption is also observed.

Reactions involving Bromine.

(a) *Potassium oxalate and bromine*.—Bhattacharya and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 523) have shown that this reaction is appreciably accelerated by radiations of wave-lengths 7304 and 8500Å, although the limits of sensitised decomposition and photochemical dissociation for molecules of bromine are 6300 and 5100Å. Fig. 2 shows that the light absorption by a mixture of a solution of potassium oxalate and bromine water containing hydrochloric acid is greater than those of the two ingredients taken separately. Here again we find that the presence of an oxalate sensitises the decomposition of bromine molecules and makes them reactive in radiations of longer wave-lengths and the light absorption is markedly increased due to the weakening of the Br—Br linking.

(b) *Tartaric acid and bromine*.—Ghosh and collaborators (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 165; 1928, 5, 342, 361) studied this reaction carefully in radiations of wave-lengths 4500-4900Å and Bhattacharya and Dhar (*ibid.*, 1929, 6, 451) investigated the reaction between Rochelle salt and bromine in radiations of wave-length 7304Å, which markedly accelerate the reaction. The limits of sensitised decomposition and photochemical dissociation of bromine molecules are 6300 and 5100Å. Hence in presence of Rochelle salt, the dissociation of bromine molecules is markedly sensitised and these molecules become reactive in radiations of wave-lengths longer than the sensitised and photochemical dissociation limits of bromine. Along with this increased reactivity of bromine molecules, a marked increase of light absorption is observed as will be evident from Fig. 3.

Reactions involving Iodine.

(a) *Potassium oxalate and iodine*.—It has been stated in Part I (*loc. cit.*) that in presence of an oxalate, the dissociation of iodine molecules is sensitised. Fig. 2 shows that the light absorption by a mixture of iodine and potassium oxalate solutions is much greater than those of iodine and oxalate considered separately.

(b) *Sodium formate and iodine*.—This reaction is also accelerated by radiations of wave-lengths 7304 and 8500Å, the limits of sensitised decomposition and photochemical dissociation for iodine molecules being 8050 and 4995Å respectively. Fig. 4 shows that the light absorption by a mixture of sodium formate and iodine is much greater than those of the reaction mixture considered separately.

(c) *Acetone and iodine* (in presence of HCl as a catalyst).—This reaction has been studied by Bhattacharya and Dhar (*cf.* Dhar, "Chemical Action of Light," 1931, p. 161) in radiations of different wave-lengths including 7304Å. It appears, therefore, that in presence of acetone, the photo-dissociation of iodine molecules is sensitised. It is clear from Fig. 5 that a mixture of aqueous acetone and iodine shows greater absorption than the two substances taken separately.

(d) *Ferrous sulphate and iodine*.—Bhattacharya and Dhar (*cf.* Dhar, "Chemical Action of Light," 1931, p. 162) investigated this reaction in radiations of wave-lengths 7304 and 8500Å and hence the photo

dissociation of iodine molecules is sensitised by the presence of the reducing agent, ferrous sulphate. It will appear from Fig. 6 that the light absorption by a mixture of ferrous sulphate and iodine is appreciably greater than those of the two ingredients estimated separately.

(e) *Sodium nitrite and iodine*.—Bhattacharya and Dhar (*cf.* "Chemical Action of Light," p. 163) observed that this reaction is appreciably accelerated by radiations of wave-lengths 7304 and 8500Å. It appears that the presence of sodium nitrite sensitises the dissociation of iodine molecules. The light absorption by a mixture of sodium nitrite and iodine is much greater than the absorptions due to sodium nitrite and iodine taken individually (*cf.* Fig. 7).

(f) *Sodium tartrate and iodine*.—This reaction has been found to be accelerated by radiations of wave-lengths 7304 and 8500Å and hence it is believed that the presence of sodium tartrate sensitises the dissociation of iodine molecules. Fig. 8 shows that the light absorption by a mixture of sodium tartrate and iodine is much higher than that by sodium tartrate and iodine considered separately.

(g) *Sodium lactate and iodine*.—Radiations of wave-lengths 7304 and 8500Å accelerate the reaction between sodium lactate and iodine and thus in this case also, the dissociation of iodine molecules is made more easy due to the presence of the reducing agent, sodium lactate. The light absorption by a mixture of sodium lactate and iodine is greater than those by the two substances when observed separately (*cf.* Fig. 9).

(h) *Sodium malonate and iodine*.—This reaction also takes place at a greater speed in radiations of wave-lengths 7304 and 8500Å than in the dark and hence the presence of the reducing agent sodium malonate sensitises the dissociation of iodine molecules. A mixture of sodium malonate and iodine shows a greater light absorption than solutions of sodium malonate and iodine taken individually (*cf.* Fig. 10).

(i) *Sodium malate and iodine*.—Radiations of wave-lengths 7340Å accelerate this reaction and hence the presence of sodium malate makes the iodine molecules more reactive and this is also corroborated by the increased light absorption by the mixture than the two ingredients considered separately (*cf.* Fig. 11).

(j) *Sodium citrate and iodine*.—The reaction takes place at a greater velocity in radiations of wave-length 7304Å than in the dark

and hence the dissociation of iodine molecules is sensitised by the presence of sodium citrate. Moreover, the absorption of light by a mixture of sodium citrate and iodine solution is much greater than that by sodium citrate and iodine considered separately (cf. Fig. 12).

(k) *Hydroxylamine hydrochloride and iodine*.—This reaction is accelerated by radiations of wave-lengths 7304 and 8500Å and hence due to the presence of hydroxylamine hydrochloride, the photo-dissociation of iodine is facilitated. Fig. 13 shows that the light absorption by a mixture of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and iodine is more pronounced than that by hydroxylamine hydrochloride and iodine taken separately.

(l) *Hydrazine sulphate and iodine*.—This reaction takes place in radiations of wave-lengths 7304 and 8500Å at a speed greater than that in the dark and hence the presence of hydrazine sulphate sensitises the photochemical decomposition of iodine molecules. Moreover, the light absorption by a mixture of hydrazine sulphate and iodine as shown in Fig. 14 is much greater than the absorptions of hydrazine sulphate and iodine considered separately.

(m) *Hypophosphorous acid and iodine*.—This reaction was studied in the dark by Steele (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 1641). Dhar reported that it was light sensitive. The light absorption by the mixture in this case also is much greater than the absorptions due to iodine and hypophosphorous acid taken separately (cf. Fig 15).

(n) *Phosphorous acid and iodine*.—The kinetics of this reaction have been investigated only in the dark by Steele (*ibid.*, 1908, 93, 2203).

In this case also the light absorption by the mixture is appreciably greater than that caused by phosphorous acid and iodine considered separately (cf. Fig. 16). It is of interest to note that both the velocity of the reaction and the light absorption are greater in the reaction between hypophosphorous acid and iodine than in the reaction between phosphorous acid and iodine.

Reactions involving Chromic Acid.

(a) *Quinine sulphate and chromic acid*.—The oxidation of quinine sulphate by chromic acid has been investigated in different radiations as well as in the dark by several investigators, notably Goldberg (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1902, 41, 1; *Z. wiss. Phot.*, 1906, 4, 56), Luther

and Forbes (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **31**, 770), Dhar and collaborators (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **111**, 717; "Chemical Action of Light", 1931, p. 190), Forbes and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 1891; 1933, **55**, 588). Both the reacting substances showed marked light absorption but the mixture absorbs more than the ingredients taken separately as will be evident from Fig 17.

(b) *Oxalic acid and chromic acid.*—This reaction has been investigated by Dhar and collaborators in the dark and in light. Fig. 17 shows that the light absorption by a mixture of oxalic acid and chromic acid is appreciably greater than that by oxalic acid and chromic acid considered separately.

(c) *Formic acid and chromic acid.*—This reaction has been studied by Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **111**, 707) in the dark. It appears from Fig 17 that the light absorption by a mixture of formic acid and chromic acid is slightly greater than that by the two substances considered individually.

(d) *Hypophosphorous acid and chromic acid.*—Chromic acid is easily reduced to chromium salts in presence of hypophosphorous acid. Fig. 18 shows that the light absorption by a mixture of chromic acid and hypophosphorous acid is appreciably greater than that by chromic acid and hypophosphorous acid taken separately.

(e) *Phosphorous acid and chromic acid.*—This reaction was first studied by Dhar (*Ann. chim.*, 1919, *ix*, **11**, 130) in the dark. Fig. 18 shows that the light absorption by a mixture containing dilute solutions of phosphorous acid and chromic acid is greater than that by the two acids taken separately.

Reactions involving Potassium Permanganate.

(a) *Oxalic acid and potassium permanganate.*—This reaction has been investigated by several workers notably Harcourt and Esson (*Phil. Trans.*, 1866, **56**, 193), Skrabal (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1904, **42**, 1), Dhar and collaborators (*cf.* Dhar, "Chemical Action of Light," 1931, p. 196) in light as well as in the dark. Fig. 19 shows that the light absorption by a mixture of potassium permanganate and oxalic acid is much greater than that by potassium permanganate and oxalic acid considered separately.

(b) *Potassium permanganate and hydrochloric acid.*—It is well known that potassium permanganate reacts quite readily with hydro-

chloric acid. In this reaction also it is observed that the light absorption by a mixture of potassium permanganate and hydrochloric acid is appreciably greater than that by the two ingredients taken individually (*cf.* Fig. 20).

Reactions involving Mercuric Chloride.

The increase in light absorption by different organic acids due to the presence of dilute solutions of mercuric chloride as observed by Ghosh and collaborators (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 871) has already been considered in Part I of this series.

We have studied the cases of the reduction of mercuric chloride by phosphorous and hypophosphorous acids.

(a) *Mercuric chloride and hypophosphorous acid*.—The kinetics of this reaction have been investigated in the dark by Mitchell (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **119**, 1266). Fig. 21 shows that the light absorption by a mixture of mercuric chloride and hypophosphorous acid is appreciably greater than that by the two components taken separately,

(b) *Mercuric chloride and phosphorous acid*.—This reaction was first studied in the dark by Purkayastha and Dhar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, **121**, 156). It will be evident from Fig. 22 that the light absorption by a mixture of mercuric chloride and phosphorous acid is greater than that by mercuric chloride and phosphorous acid considered individually.

Reactions involving Silver Nitrate.

(a) *Silver nitrate and sodium formate*.—Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **111**, 707) studied this reaction in the dark. Fig. 23 shows that the light absorption by a mixture of silver nitrate and sodium formate is appreciably greater than that by silver nitrate and sodium formate considered separately.

(b) *Silver nitrate and ferrous ammonium sulphate*.—Dhar, Datta, and Bhattacharya (*Proc. K. Akad. Wetensch. Amsterdam*, 1920, **23**, 259) and recently Roberts and Soper (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2004) studied this reaction in the dark. The light absorption by a mixture of silver nitrate and ferrous ammonium sulphate is much greater than that by the two ingredients taken individually (*cf.* Fig. 24).

Reactions involving Hydrogen Peroxide.

(a) *Hydrogen peroxide and sodium thiosulphate.*—Abel (*Monatsh.*, 1907, 28, 1239) has shown that hydrogen peroxide reacts with thiosulphate according to the equation

Fig. 25 shows that the light absorption by a mixture of sodium thiosulphate and hydrogen peroxide is greater than that by the two constituents considered separately.

(b) *Hydrogen peroxide and glucose.*—Ghosh and Mukherji (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 231) have studied the photo-oxidation of glucose and hydrogen peroxide in presence of tungstic acid sol. Fig. 26 shows that a mixture consisting of dilute solution of glucose and hydrogen peroxide absorbs light to a greater extent than the sum of the two ingredients considered separately.

It is well known that the oxidation of organic substances by hydrogen peroxide is accelerated by iron salts. Both ferrous and ferric salts are effective. We have observed that the addition of ferric chloride increases the light absorption by a mixture of hydrogen peroxide and an organic substance.

(c) *Hydrogen peroxide and potassium persulphate.*—This reaction was first studied by Friend (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 1096) in the dark. The light absorption by a mixture consisting of dilute solutions of hydrogen peroxide and potassium persulphate is appreciably greater than that by the two substances taken separately (cf. Fig. 27).

Reactions involving Oxygen.

Recently Dhar and Atma Ram (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 287) have shown that organic substances like acetic acid, aminoacetic acid, glycerol, acetone, etc., are appreciably oxidised first to formaldehyde when they are exposed to air and light.

We have taken photographs of dilute solutions of acetic and aminoacetic acids before and after saturation of the solutions with oxygen in a large Hilger quartz spectrograph. Fig. 28 shows that the light absorption in the short ultraviolet region is appreciably greater with the solutions of acetic and aminoacetic acids when saturated with oxygen than in the absence of oxygen, which when dissolved in water shows slight absorption in the ultraviolet. From the figure it will be evident that the light absorption by a mixture of

acetic acid or aminoacetic acid and oxygen is slightly greater than that by the two ingredients considered separately.

As the beginning of molecular absorption of oxygen is in the region 2020\AA , it is not possible to obtain more marked difference in absorption in the ultraviolet region with mixture of oxygen in an ordinary quartz spectrograph.

Iodic acid and oxalic acid.—The kinetics of this reaction in the dark and in light have been studied in this laboratory. Fig. 29 shows that the light absorption by a mixture of iodic and oxalic acids is greater than the absorptions of the two acids taken individually.

Hydrolysis of Cane Sugar.

The kinetics of this reaction has played an important rôle in the development of chemical dynamics and photochemistry. In publications from this laboratory it has been shown that this reaction is accelerated not only by ultraviolet light but also by radiations of wave-lengths 4725 , 5650 , 7304 and 8500\AA .

It will be of interest to note from Fig. 30 that the light absorption by a mixture of hydrochloric acid and cane sugar is appreciably greater than that by cane sugar and hydrochloric acid taken separately.

DISCUSSION.

It has already been emphasised in Part I (*loc. cit.*) that the researches of Franck and Victor Henri show that whenever a molecule is rendered active and unstable, either by absorption of light or increase of temperature, and there is a loosening of the bond uniting the atoms, an increased light absorption by the molecules in this active condition is of common occurrence. Moreover, the experimental results brought forward in this and the previous papers are in support of the view that molecules can also be activated and there is consequent weakening of the binding forces by chemical agencies and this is evident by increased light absorption. Thus the binding forces of the halogen molecules, chlorine, bromine and iodine are weakened by the presence of reducing agents like hydrogen, sodium nitrite, ferrous sulphate, organic acids and their salts, etc., and in every case whenever there is the possibility of a chemical change between a halogen molecule and a reducing agent, and a weakening of the binding forces of the atoms in the halogen molecules takes place, it has always been observed that the light absorption by the mixture of the

two reacting substances is appreciably greater than the absorption due to the individual substances considered separately. Similar results have been obtained with other reacting substances. On the other hand, when there is no chemical change by mixing two substances, no increased light absorption is observed as is evident in the photographs taken with hydrochloric acid and oxalic acid singly or in mixture (*cf.* Fig. 31).

From the numerous cases cited in this paper it seems clear to us that if there is the possibility of the occurrence of a chemical change by mixing two or more substances, increased light absorption by the mixture is likely to be observed in those cases. We are of opinion that the increased light absorption by a mixture in comparison with those of the ingredients is likely to be a measure of the reactivity of a given mixture of two or more substances.

Over and above the important experimental results of Ghosh and collaborators (*loc. cit.*) on increased light absorption by mixtures already discussed from this point of view in Part I, the following observations by Ghosh and Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 823, 871) are of interest. These authors have observed a very marked increase in the extinction coefficient of mixtures containing a very dilute solution of copper sulphate and sodium sulphite in the red region. Moreover, it is well known that a copper salt is an excellent positive catalyst in the oxidation of sodium sulphite solution by oxygen. The above authors have also shown that the extinction coefficients of mixtures of Fehling's solution or Benedict's solution with reducing agents like glucose, glycerol, sodium formate, etc., are much greater in ultraviolet radiations of wave-lengths varying from 3750-2266Å than those of the ingredients considered separately. These observations are in support of our theory that the weakening of the binding forces of the molecules of cupric salts due to the presence of reducing agents leads to an increased light absorption. Recently Damon and Daniels (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 2363) have observed that the green fluorescence of acetone vapour is replaced by a less bright blue fluorescence by the introduction of oxygen. The authors are of opinion that even in absence of oxygen the fluorescent radiations of acetone contain blue rays, which are masked by the more intense green fluorescence and that the oxidation, instead of producing a blue fluorescence, merely quenches the green and permits the blue to be more prominent. Fluorescence of acetone vapour on illumination has been found to be a comparatively

unimportant factor in the photolysis and photo-oxidation of acetone. Similar results in which the introduction of oxygen causes the decrease of light emission of acetone vapour have also been observed by Crone and Norrish (*Nature*, 1933, **132**, 241). These authors have claimed that they were the first to observe in the fluorescent spectra the phenomenon of predissociation, which has been generally observed in the absorption spectra only, but Turner (*Phys. Rev.*, 1932, **41**, 627) has also recorded the phenomenon of predissociation in the fluorescence spectra of iodine vapour. The decrease in the light emission of acetone vapour on illumination in presence of oxygen is in agreement with our view that increase in the chemical reactivity of acetone due to the presence of oxygen leads to the increase in the light absorption. Similar results are obtained with iodine vapour. It is known that predissociation of molecules can be induced or increased by collisions in some cases and atoms of iodine are generated in iodine vapour when illuminated by radiations of wave-lengths less than 5100\AA if argon is present. The argon quenches the fluorescence of the higher vibrational states of the iodine molecules.

It is well known that the phenomenon of adsorption of a substance on a surface is more or less allied to chemical combination. Recently deBoer and Custers (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1933, **B**, **21**, 208) have shown that the light absorption of iodine adsorbed on a CaF_2 film is much greater than that of gaseous or dissolved iodine in water.

The views advanced in this paper are also supported by the observations of Fajans and Karagunis (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, **B**, **5**, 385) on the light absorption by silver iodide. The authors have shown that the light absorption by silver iodide containing adsorbed silver is appreciably greater than that of silver iodide, containing adsorbed iodine or silver iodide alone. Moreover, it is well known that the silver halides containing adsorbed silver are more photo-sensitive and hence more liable to be decomposed in light than the silver halides containing an excess of the halogen. Similar results have been obtained with other silver halides. The presence of silver sensitises the photo-decomposition of silver halides and weakens the binding forces between silver and the halogen atoms and causes increased light absorption.

The observations of Vogt and Kôenigsberger (*Z. Physik*, 1923, **13**, 292) on the influence of temperature on the continuous absorption of

bromine and iodine and of Gibson and Bayliss (*Phys. Rev.*, 1933, **44**, 188) with chlorine seem to show that increased temperature leads to a general broadening of absorption.

According to London's theory of chemical attraction, the production of an additive compound, not necessarily stable, formed by mixing two or more substances is essentially the first step requiring activation in a bimolecular exchange reaction. It appears that in general the formation of an additive compound with loosening of the binding forces of the molecules and consequent increased light absorption is the first stage of a chemical reaction.

We are expecting that in many cases we shall be in a position to calculate the energy of dissociation of molecules from measurements of increased light absorption by mixtures of reacting substances.

When the light absorptions of the reactions of $K_2C_2O_4 + Cl_2$, $K_2C_2O_4 + Br_2$ and $K_2C_2O_4 + I_2$, are compared, it will be observed that the absorption due to $K_2C_2O_4 + Cl_2$ is the maximum, then comes $K_2C_2O_4 + Br_2$ and finally $K_2C_2O_4 + I_2$. The heats of the reactions as calculated from the thermochemical measurements of Thomsen are as follows: $K_2C_2O_4 + Cl_2$, 84 Cal; $K_2C_2O_4 + Br_2$, 62 Cal; $K_2C_2O_4 + I_2$, 32 Cal; but the energies of activation of the three reactions are in the reverse order, the iodine reaction has the largest and the chlorine the least energy of activation. Moreover, it is well known that the dissociation energies of the halogen molecules are as follows: Cl_2 , 57 Cal; Br_2 , 45 Cal; I_2 , 35 Cal. It seems, therefore, that the dissociation energies of halogens are in the same order as their light absorption in presence of $K_2C_2O_4$. Moreover, it should be noted that the light absorption is generally more prominent in those reactions, which proceed at a greater velocity than in those, where the velocities are small. Thus in the reactions with halogens and potassium oxalate, the velocity is maximum with chlorine and minimum with iodine and the increased light absorption of the mixtures is in the same order.

SUMMARY.

(A) It has been observed that the light absorption by a mixture of the reacting substances is greater than the absorptions by the ingredients with following reactions:

- (1) Oxalic acid and chlorine, (2) potassium oxalate and bromine,
- (3) tartaric acid and bromine, (4) potassium oxalate and iodine,

(5) sodium formate and iodine, (6) acetone and iodine, (7) ferrous sulphate and iodine, (8) sodium nitrite and iodine, (9) sodium tartrate and iodine, (10) sodium lactate and iodine, (11) sodium malonate and iodine, (12) sodium malate and iodine, (13) sodium citrate and iodine, (14) hydroxylamine hydrochloride and iodine, (15) hydrazine sulphate and iodine, (16) hypophosphorous acid and iodine, (17) phosphorous acid and iodine, (18) quinine sulphate and chromic acid, (19) oxalic acid and chromic acid, (20) formic acid and chromic acid, (21) hypophosphorous acid and chromic acid, (22) phosphorous acid and chromic acid, (23) oxalic acid and potassium permanganate, (24) hydrochloric acid and potassium permanganate, (25) mercuric chloride and hypophosphorous acid, (26) mercuric chloride and phosphorous acid, (27) silver nitrate and sodium formate, (28) silver nitrate and ferrous ammonium sulphate, (29) hydrogen peroxide and sodium thiosulphate, (30) hydrogen peroxide and glucose, (31) hydrogen peroxide and potassium persulphate, (32) acetic acid and oxygen, (33) glycine and oxygen, (34) iodic acid and oxalic acid, (35) hydrolysis of cane sugar.

(B) The increased light absorption appears to be due to the activation of the molecules by the presence of the molecules of the other substances. The activation of the molecules is associated with the weakening of their binding forces and consequent increased light absorption.

(C) The observation of Weigert and Kellermann on increased light absorption by a mixture of chlorine and hydrogen and the increased light absorption observed by Ghosh and collaborators with mixture of Fehling's or Benedict's solutions and mixtures of reducing agents, and the observations of Fajans on increased light absorption by silver halides containing adsorbed silver, have been explained from the view point that the chemical reactivity of these various systems is associated with the weakening of the binding force and increased light absorption.

(D) The reactions with greater velocity appear to show greater light absorption than those with small velocities.

(E) It seems that the energies of dissociation of some molecules can be determined from measurements of increased light absorption by mixtures.

2149 2294 2618 3274 5153Å

FIG. 1.
Exposure—15"

Arc
N/20—H₂C₂O₄
N/150—Cl₂ (with HCl)
N/10—H₂C₂O₄ and
N/75—Cl₂ (with HCl)

FIG. 2.
Exposure—7"

The velocity of the reaction of K₂C₂O₄ with halogens is in the order Cl₂ > Br₂ > I₂. The light absorption follows the same order.

Arc
N/2—K₂C₂O₄
N/300—Cl₂(HCl)
N—K₂C₂O₄ and
N/150—Cl₂
N/300—Br₂ (HCl)
N—K₂C₂O₄ and
N/150—Br₂
N/300—I₂(HCl)
N—K₂C₂O₄ +
N/150—I₂

FIG. 3.
Exposure—15"

N/700—Br₂
N/23·8—tartaric acid
N/350—Br₂ + N/11·9-tartaric acid

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FIG. 4.

Exposure—20"
The velocity of the reaction between Na-formate + I₂ > K₂C₂O₄ + I₂. Light absorption is in the same order.

Arc

N/700—I₂

N/4—Na-formate

N/2—Na-formate
+ N/350—I₂

FIG. 5.

Exposure—30"

Arc

0.26% Acetone (HCl)

N/700—I₂ (HCl)

0.5% Acetone +
N/350—I₂ (HCl)

FIG. 6.

Exposure—7"

Arc

N/1200—I₂

1% FeSO₄

N/600—I₂ + 2% FeSO₄

2079 2149 2294 2618 3274 5153 Å

FIG. 7.
Exposure—7"

Arc
N/700— I_2
N/16.8— $NaNO_2$
N/350— I_2 + N/8.4
— $NaNO_2$

FIG. 8.
Exposure—7"

Arc
N/500— I_2
N/2— Na -tartrate
N/250— I_2 + Na -
tartrate

FIG. 9.
Exposure—7"

Arc
N/700— I_2
N/2— Na -lactate
N/350— I_2 + Na -
lactate

FIG. 10.
Exposure—7"

Arc
N/700— I_2
N/17.6— Na -malonate
N/350— I_2 +
N/8.8— Na -malate

2149 2294 2618 3274 5153Å

FIG. 11.
Exposure—7"

Arc
N/700— I_2
N/27—Na-malate
N/350— I_2 + N/13.5—Na-malate

FIG. 12.
Exposure—7"

Arc
N/700— I_2
N/2—Na-citrate
N/350— I_2 + N—Na-citrat

FIG. 13.
Exposure—7"

Arc
N/700— I_2
N/10— $NH_2OH \cdot HCl$
N/350— I_2 +
N/5— $NH_2OH \cdot HCl$

FIG. 14.
Exposure—7"

Arc
N/700— $I_2 (H_2SO_4)$
N/8— $NH_2 \cdot NH_2 \cdot H_2SO_4 (H_2SO_4)$
N/350— I_2 + N/4— $N_2H_4, H_2SO_4 (H_2SO_4)$

2149 2291 2618 3274 5153Å

FIG. 15.
Exposure—7"
Reaction of
 $H_2PO_2 + I_2 >$
 $H_3PO_3 + I_2$
under identical
conditions.
Light absorp-
tion is greater
in the former
case than the
latter.

'rc
N/700— I_2
N/4.3— H_3PO_3
N/350— $I_2 +$
N/2.5— H_3PO_2

FIG. 16.
Exposure—7"

Arc
N/700— I_2
10.9N— H_3PO_3
N/350— $I_2 +$
21.8N— H_3PO_3

FIG. 17.
Exposure—15"
Reaction of
chromic acid +
 $C_2H_2O_4 >$
chromic acid +
 H_2CO_2 .
Light absorp-
tion is greater
in the former.

Arc
N/1656— $H_2Cr_2O_7$
0.04%—quinine
sulphate
N/828— $H_2Cr_2O_7 +$
0.08% quin. sulph.
N/11.9— CH_2O_2
N/828— $H_2Cr_2O_7 +$
N/5.95— CH_2O_2
N/200— $C_2H_2O_4$
N/828— $H_2Cr_2O_7 +$
N/100— $C_2H_2O_4$

2149 2294 2168 3274 153A

FIG. 18.
Exposure—15"
Reaction of
chromic acid +
 $H_3PO_2 >$
chromic acid +
 H_3PO_3 . The
former absorbs
more light.

Arc
N/119— H_3PO_2
N/2232— $H_2Cr_2O_7$
N/59.5— H_3PO_3 +
N/1116— $H_2Cr_2O_7$
N/14.3— H_3PO_2
N/7.15— H_3PO_2 +
N/1116— $H_2Cr_2O_7$

FIG. 19.
Exposure—15"

Arc
N/200— $KMnO_4$
N/40— $C_2H_2O_4$
N/100— $KMnO_4$ +
N/20— $C_2H_2O_4$

FIG. 20.
Exposure—15"

Arc
N/800— $KMnO_4$
N/2—HCl
N/400— $KMnO_4$ +
N—HCl

2149 2294 2618 3274 5153A

FIG. 21.
Exposure—7"

Arc
N/14·3— H_3PO_2
N/18— $HgCl_2$
N/7·15— P_3PO_2 +
N/9— $HgCl_2$

FIG. 22.
Exposure—7"

Arc
N/119— H_3PO_3
N/36— $HgCl_2$
N/59·5— H_3PO_3 +
N/18— $HgCl_2$

FIG. 23.
Exposure—7"
Reaction of
 $AgNO_3$ + Fe-
Am. sulphate
appears faster
than $AgNO_3$ +
 NaH_2CO_2 -
Former absorbs
more light.

0·5% $AgNO_3$
0·5% $NaHCO_2$
1% $AgNO_3$ +
1% $NaHCO_2$

FIG. 24.
Exposure—7"

Arc
0·5% $AgNO_3$
1% Fe Am. Sulphate
1% $AgNO_3$ +
2% Fe Am.
sulphate.

2149 2294 2618 3274 5153^oÅ

FIG. 25.
Exposure—15"

Arc

0.184% H₂O₂

N/982 — Na₂S₂O₃

0.368% H₂O₂ + N/491
Na₂S₂O₃

FIG. 26.
Exposure—15"

Arc

0.0184% H₂O₂

1.25% glucose

0.0368% H₂O₂ + 2.5%
glucose

FIG. 27.
Exposure—15"

1% K₂S₂O₈

0.184% H₂O₂

0.368% H₂O₂ + 2%
K₂S₂O₈

FIG. 28.

Exposure—30"

1. Arc.
2. Water saturated in oxygen.
3. N/40 Acetic acid
4. N/40-Acetic acid saturated with O₂.
5. N/40-Glycine.
6. N/40-Glycine saturated with O₂.
7. Distilled water.

2618

3274

5153^oA

FIG. 29.
Exposure—15"

$N/20 - \text{HIO}_3$

$N/10 - \text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$

$N/10 - \text{HIO}_3 + N/5 - \text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$

FIG. 30.
Exposure—15"

Arc

20% Cane sugar

$N/40 - \text{HCl}$

40% Cane sugar +
 $N/20 - \text{HCl}$

FIG. 31.
Exposure—15"

Arc

$N/40 - \text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4$

$N/80 - \text{HCl}$

$N/20 - \text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_4 +$
 $N/40 - \text{HCl}$